

Creating Occupational Health and Safety Culture within the Scope of Social Responsibility Role and Function of Public Relations

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Creating Occupational Health and Safety Culture within the Scope of Social Responsibility Role and Function of Public Relations

Abstract

The fact that it is not enough for corporations to produce only and provide service to the society also requires them to conduct their activities with a sense of social responsibility for a sustainable corporate success. While the conditions and criteria for institutions to have an advantageous position in the eyes of the society through CSR practices, it should be included that they differentiate their institutions in a socially sensitive manner, value their employees and include them in the scope of social responsibility. It should not be overlooked that it will play an active role. In this context, it is important that the occupational health and safety culture is evaluated together with sincere and sustainable occupational health and safety efforts for companies that take it into the scope of social responsibility. Obviously, this will make their institutions more credible in the eyes of the public. Occupational Health and Safety and Corporate Social Responsibility issues are gaining more importance in Turkey and in the world. This situation should not be considered as issues that concern only employers and employees, but should be associated with economic production efficiency, social health and social peace. The sustainability of the existence of institutions is closely related to their contribution to the society by offering products and services so that they can develop and become stronger. Again, it is necessary to reiterate that they should attach importance to laws, ethical rules and social responsibility efforts to make the society they live in better. It should be underlined that sustainable corporate success will only be possible if institutions gain a better appearance in the eyes of the public through social responsibility projects. Because it is especially important to create an occupational health and safety culture due to the ethical and social responsibilities of institutions as well as their economic and legal responsibilities. From this point of view, for example, the most important condition for preventing accidents is to create and maintain an occupational health and safety culture by effectively implementing public relations and social

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responsibility activities. In this article, "Social Responsibility Role and Function of Public Relations in Creating Occupational Health and Safety Culture" will be determined.

Keywords: *Public Relations, Public Relations and Social Responsibility Role, Public Relations and Its Function, Occupational Health and Safety Culture, Occupational Health and Safety, Corporate Social Responsibility*

1. Introduction

OHS studies are based on preventive approaches in health and safety. In addition, it is important to develop a management style for the prevention of work accidents and occupational diseases. Because the fact that it is one of the most important conditions for the participation of the employees requires an effective public relations work of the enterprises to realize these; Creating an OHS culture lies at the heart of this.

As we stated in the abstract, the aim of this study is to investigate the functional relations, roles and functions of Archie Carrol's classical social responsibility pyramid qualitatively and quantitatively, and to the stages of "public relations", "corporate culture" and "occupational health and safety culture". It would be correct to examine the parameters of "economic (basic) responsibilities", "legal (mandatory) responsibilities", "ethical (conscientious) responsibilities" and "voluntary (social) responsibilities". In addition to the fact that public relations have used different communication channels and methods, as they aim to offer solutions to the problems they encounter to the owners and managers of the institutions, they have been defined in a different way because they are shaped according to the expectations of the institutions, they are defined differently by institutions and practitioners, and everyone agrees. a definition could not be made (Bıçakçı, 2002:114).

As seen in all social sciences, although dealing with abstract concepts is one of the main problems in the field of public relations, it is normal that a single approach is not sufficient since the main area of interest is human. This results in varying approaches. However, as in every social science, it should not be ignored that public relations have both a scientific and an artistic aspect. The scientific aspect of public relations should be expressed in terms of being able to use different technologies, being able to be transferred to other people, and being a

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human-centered science. Again, the fact that knowledge and techniques can be adapted to daily life reveals the result that one public relations practitioner can be more successful than another, due to the difference in skills. It should be noted that the fact that personal characteristics stand out and differ from practitioner to practitioner expresses the artistic aspect of public relations (Budak, 2010:5).

2. Diversity of Public Relations Activities

It should be noted that the main difference of public relations activities consists of concepts that continue to differ in definition between academics and practitioners. Because the acceptance of public relations practitioners from academic staff, researchers, students and the public on the basis of definitions of public relations is evaluated as “public relations is a strategic communication process that builds an interactive and beneficial relationship between institutions and their target audiences” (Seitel, 2016:1).). Although public relations oversee establishing a bond with the society and customers of the institutions operating in the private sector or public institutions, the elements of communication, support and trust constitute the whole of systematic and organized work. On this, Tortop (2010) public relations; “It is the function of making the people adopt the policy followed by the administration, announcing the work continuously and fully, creating a positive atmosphere towards the administration, as well as knowing what the people think about the administration and what they expect from the administration, and ensuring cooperation with the public.” defined as (Tortop, 2009: 4). Again, the fact that public relations is not only a concept to be passed over with a theoretical definition, but also a discipline, is a supportive definition, while shedding light on our examination criteria and findings in our study (Küçüksaraç, 2008: 171). In Turkey, Asna (1983) gave the first lectures on public relations, and this discipline was defined as: “Private and legal persons establishing and developing honest and solid ties with the specified masses, directing them to positive beliefs and actions, evaluating the reactions, directing the attitude, mutually beneficial relations. It is an art of management that includes planned efforts to continue” (Asna, 2012:23). Again, Budak and Budak (2010) public relations; It summarizes it as "establishing relations of a person or organization with other persons or organizations to gain an interest" and completes

it as "all activities to improve existing relations". It would be appropriate to support these relations with the concept of "image engineering" (Budak, 2010:8). Because Bernays (1923) states that all efforts to integrate the persuasion and attitude and behavior necessary for the knowledge, attitude and behavior of the target audience summarize the concept and discipline of "public relations" (Seitel, 2016:5). It is one of the management functions that guides public relations to determine the needs of the services, activities and continuous information, to solve their problems, to use the wishes and impulses with professional communication methods, to provide feedback about the target audiences and to offer products and services according to their expectations. In this context, since public relations is an activity that distinguishes an institution, it is an appropriate characterization that it is activities that provide two-way information flow by interacting with professional methods (Mihçioğlu, 1971: 93).

3. Professionalism in Public Relations

A professional public relations specialist is expected to adhere to ethical principles, to remain true to integrity, and to develop appropriate strategies (Sabuncuoğlu, 1996:26). Because, being as close as possible to the top management, making the voice of the institution heard to internal and external audiences, conveying the demands of the target audience to the top management of the institution, determining the strategy according to these are the main topics of the objectives that fit the definition. The fact that the organizations at the lower levels are far from the top management will make it difficult to adequately examine and direct the employees inside the institution and the target audience outside the institution in terms of public relations (Budak, 2010:185). Here, according to Carroll (1991), to increase the earnings per share of the shareholders, to work with this goal, to use the production factors as well as to make a profit, to maintain its strong position against other institutions, to keep the productivity level at the highest level, to use resources in the most efficient way and to do the best. aims to meet the needs of the society with the resources of the institution, summarizes the ideal institutional structure. Although it is not a legal obligation for the institution not to fulfill its responsibilities in this dimension, it should be stated that it will damage the reputation of the institution in the eyes of the society. Again, while Carroll (1991) claims that each stage is related to the previous stage with his four-stage model, he also includes the marketing activities of the institution to

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achieve a social purpose in professionalism. Preston and Post (1981), in this regard, include the quality and strength of all interactions with corporate interaction, customers, employees, shareholders and credit providers. In this regard, it is necessary to evaluate the compulsory interactions of the institution and the social problems with the society and the legal and ethical issues in question should be included in its interactions with the government and society.

4. Concepts of Ethics and Responsibility

According to Certo and Peter (1991), the following assumptions support the points we have underlined in our study: “The institution should form a structure that interacts with the society; should calculate and decide on the returns and expenses of an activity; he should calculate the cost of every activity he will do, he should have the responsibility of dealing with the other problems of the society”. Here, it is necessary to state that it is the social responsibility of the institutions to make new initiatives to increase their profits and to contribute more to the society by producing new products (Milton Friedman, 1970). Because, fulfilling the social responsibility of the institution in the best way (Friedman, 1970: 32), the social responsibility of the institutions towards the society they serve is also related to bringing together the scarce resources and making them useful for the society (Baron, 1993: 507). The fact that the SA 8000 Social Responsibility Standard, which was created by the International Social Responsibility Organization to provide a standard for social responsibility and improve the conditions of employees, was published in 1997 strengthens this statement. Because, the contributions of the SA 8000 Standard can be summarized as the opportunity of employees to organize and make collective agreements, the preparation of employee rights in an appropriate environment and the awareness of institutions. Because, as well as the SA 8000 standard, the ISO 26000 Social Responsibility Standard, being a standard that shows commitment to sustainable development and community support, requires the concepts of "being ethical" and "responsibility" (ISO 26000, 2010).

In this regard, it is obvious that public relations, as it interacts with the corporate culture, affects and is affected by the corporate culture (Öksüz, 2014:79). After these stages, the institution will be able to take firm steps towards becoming a strong institution (Griffin and Moohead,

2010:473). Again, it is necessary to state that public relations are a key factor in increasing the reputation of the company together with the strengthening of communication within and outside the institution (Öksüz, 2014: 83).

5. Archie Carroll's Social Responsibility Pyramid Scoring Criteria and Findings

Research data on the concepts of "basic responsibility", "obligatory responsibility", "conscientious responsibility" and "social responsibility" were examined in the study of applying an attitude scale to the employees of the institution regarding the determination of "Basic Responsibilities" regarding Public Relations in institutions, using the survey technique and paper and pencil. and factor analysis was applied. To determine the social responsibility level of the institution, another attitude scale, to determine the "conscientious responsibilities" in terms of the Corporate Culture, expressed the sense of responsibility. The results show whether the institution covers the food, transportation and health expenses of the employees, whether the salary received from the institution is sufficient and the institution's food, transportation and health expenses of the employees in line with the data obtained by the survey technique according to Archie Carroll's Social Responsibility Pyramid Scoring Criteria. It is "expected" with a high score of 3.9313 , and it has been concluded that employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities. Here, according to Archie Carroll's Social Responsibility Pyramid Scoring Criteria, the adequacy of the salary received from the institution in accordance with the survey technique data gave a “desirable” result, and its employees demanded the adequacy of the wage; but it has emerged that there is no definite expectation or necessity. Based on Archie Carroll's Social Responsibility Pyramid Scoring Criteria, according to the data obtained from the survey technique, it is "desirable" for the institution to reward its employees financially when successful, with a high score of 2,8550. From this, it has been revealed that the employees of the institution want to be rewarded financially, but there is no definite expectation or necessity.

Based on this survey and data, the relevant scale, according to Archie Carroll's Social Responsibility Pyramid Scoring Criteria, states that “the institution covers the food, transportation and health expenses of the employees”, “the salary you receive from the

institution is sufficient” and “the institution rewards you financially when you are successful. ” questions were “expected” with an average value of 3.1985. This shows that employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities. Again, it has been found out that there are expectations about "fulfilling their social responsibilities" in terms of whether the SSI premiums of the employees are paid on time, whether the rights of female employees such as breastfeeding allowance, parental leave, maternity allowance are fulfilled, and whether an employment contract is made. Still,

In the Dimension of Mandatory Responsibility in the Institution in terms of Public Relations; According to Archie Carroll's Social Responsibility Pyramid Scoring Criteria, in line with the data obtained through the survey technique, “The institution pays the SSI premiums of the employees on time.”, “The institution fulfills the rights of women working such as breastfeeding allowance, maternity leave, maternity allowance.” and “The institution, the employment contract with its employees In order to determine the Conscientious Responsibility Level of Public Relations, questions about whether the senior management regularly evaluates the ethics training programs, whether the institution has a team working on ethics, and whether the senior management is included in the ethics training programs in the institution. were asked and the following findings were obtained.

3,7481 , and it was concluded that the employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities . As an expected and natural result, it supports the survey and the study. This is supported by the fact that, according to the criteria, in line with the data obtained by the survey technique, it is expected that the institution has an ethics team dealing with ethical issues, with a value of 3.4198. According to Archie Carroll's Social Responsibility Pyramid Scoring Criteria, the result that employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities , the top management's participation in the ethics training programs in the institution gave the result "expected" with a value of 3.3740; The conclusion that employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities also supports the basis of our work. Because “top management regularly evaluates ethics training programs in the institution”, “the institution has a team working on ethics.” and "top management takes place in ethics training programs in the institution" together, it is "expected" with an average value of 3,5139. These

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results show that employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities. The issue of encouraging its employees to work voluntarily is “expected” with a value of 3.7099. This result leads to the conclusion that employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities. It is expected that the institution attaches significant importance to its responsibilities towards society, with a value of 3.7481, and it is concluded that employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities. The application of programs that reduce the negative effects of the institution on the environment is "expected" with a value of 3.7099, and it is concluded that the employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities.

As a result, there is a sense of responsibility to protect the ethical level of the institution, based on the statements of the employees of the institution and the evaluation of the survey and scale findings and results. To disseminate ethical practices in the institution, there is a positive and significant correlation at the level of 0.01 between the adaptation of the obtained information and data to the results of the study and the relationship between the results of the availability of training programs, according to the information obtained. The results of whether the institution meets the special clothes of its employees and whether the institution meets the needs of its employees in unhygienic (dirty) environment studies were also evaluated. There was a significant positive correlation at the level of 0.01 between the relation that the institution affords the special clothes of the employees. From this, a significant positive relationship results at the level of 0.01. It is "expected" with the value of 3.4504 for the institution to organize trainings for the development of its culture, it has been concluded that the employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities . For an OHS culture to be formed, the value must be in the range of 4-5 and the Institution must give its employees the right to express their opinions. Here, for the OHS culture to be formed, the value should be in the range of 4-5, and the result that the Institution should apply the law numbered 6331 and the relevant regulations should be evaluated. Because it is "expected" with a value of 3,9008 to have a contract of employment between the institution and the employees. It is concluded that the employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities. In line with the data obtained, when the questions "the institution applies the law numbered 6331 and the relevant regulations", "the institution and the employees have a starting contract" and "the institution pays the SSI premiums of the employees on time" are evaluated together, it is

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"expected" with an average value of 3.7710, This shows that employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities. Again, when the questions "because the institution does not put pressure on its employees, there will be a voluntary working environment", "the employees do their job with pleasure because the institution trusts its employees" and "the work efficiency increases because the institution satisfies its employees financially", the average reached is 3.3435. It was concluded that the employees have expectations from their institutions to fulfill their social responsibilities.

6. "Establishment of OHS culture" in the dimension of "Social Responsibility" in the Institution

On the subject of "Establishment of an OHS culture" in the dimension of "Social Responsibility" in the institution; It is important that the institution not only encourages its employees to work voluntarily, but also attaches immense importance to its responsibilities towards society. In this regard, it is also important to evaluate the application of programs that reduce the negative effects on the environment, as well as the implementation of policies that improve the talents and careers of the employees of the institution. In addition to following flexible policies that ensure the establishment of a work life and private life balance of its employees, it also emphasizes the fact that the institution should be a voluntary work environment, since it does not put pressure on its employees. It should be underlined that the necessity of increasing the working efficiency since the institution trusts its employees, that the employees do their job with pleasure and that they satisfy their employees financially.

As a summary of the above data, evaluation of the results,

- a. *meeting the food, transportation and health expenses of the employees,*
- b. *sufficient salary,*
- c. *rewarding its employees financially when they are successful,*
- d. *investing in its employees for access to written, verbal and virtual information,*
- e. *making a program for its employees for their customs and traditions,*
- f. *ceremonies for its employees on special (holidays, public holidays, etc.) days,*
- g. *providing its employees with personal protective equipment,*

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- h. to meet the special clothes of its employees,*
- i. meeting the needs of employees in unhygienic (dirty) environment works,*
- j. Timely payment of SSI premiums,*
- k. breastfeeding allowance for female employees,*
- l. fulfilling rights such as parental leave, maternity allowance,*
- m. making employment contract,*
- n. Organizing trainings for the development of corporate culture,*
- o. giving its employees the right to express their opinions, giving the right to participate in sharing the corporate culture,*
- p. Implementation of the law numbered 6331 and related regulations and having an employment contract between employees,*
- q. regular evaluation of ethics training programs by senior management,*
- r. Having a team working on ethics,*
- s. Involvement of senior management in ethics training programs,*
- t. employees have a sense of responsibility to protect the ethical level of the organization,*
- u. the existence of training programs to promote positive ethical practices,*
- v. the organization undergoes regular ethical audits,*
- w. protection of corporate culture, ethical reputation among employees,*
- x. Having training programs aimed at creating a strong ethical culture, regular ethical auditing of the institution,*
- y. encouraging its employees to work voluntarily,*
- z. attaches immense importance to its responsibilities towards society,*
- aa. implementing programs that reduce negative impacts on the environment,*
- bb. implementing policies that improve the talents and careers of its employees,*
- cc. to follow flexible policies that ensure the establishment of a work life and private life balance of its employees,*
- dd. supporting employees who want to receive training,*
- ee. It is a voluntary working environment as it does not put pressure on its employees,*
- ff. Employees do their jobs lovingly because they trust their employees,*

requires the analysis of the data under sub-headings because of the evaluation. In other words, it seems essential to fulfill the requirements in each of the economic, legal, ethical and social responsibility areas for the formation of an OHS culture.

7. Evaluation of Corporate Culture together with Safety Culture

Expressing the concept of culture in the sense of "man's lifestyle" first emerged in the 1750s. According to Taylor, who made the most referenced definition of that period, "culture is a complex whole that includes knowledge, faith, art and morals, customs and traditions, as well as habits and even all skills acquired by the individual as a member of the society to which he belongs". (Köse and Unal, 2003:2). It is important to state that culture, in addition to containing a meaning formed in the development stages of human society, is the whole of the elements (for example, the unity of emotion, thought and judgment) that are used to transfer these values to the next generations and express the measure of the dominance of the individual and social environment of the human being (Güçlü, 2003). :149). Again, according to Aydınli (2003), culture; It is a set of beliefs, norms and values that form the basis of human behavior and make it predictable in a way, directing it towards common goals or aiming to protect some accepted situations (Aydınli, 2003: 85).

In terms of behavioral sciences, culture is passed on from one generation to the next. As it is a way of life brought to the individual from the society, it is the environment of the individual that includes the material and spiritual elements created by the other individuals in the society. ("Occupational Health and Safety Culture") According to Goodenough , culture is the information system or standards that a person uses in perceiving, believing, evaluating and taking action (Baş, 2010: 2). Culture can be defined as a set of beliefs, acceptances, rules, and norms that are shared, accepted, lived, sometimes partially changed by adding something, covering everything material and spiritual for human life. This whole distinguishes the society from others and makes it unique (Eroğlu, 2015:67).

According to Hofstede (2009), it is correct to evaluate corporate culture as "the institutional programming of the mind and mind, which distinguishes the employees of one institution from the employees of another institution" (Hofstede, 1998:2). There is a need for the existence of a

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common power that will provide support for the employees of the institution to integrate with the institution. It is the "corporate culture" that the institution and its employees create together (Köse et al., 2001: 219). Since the corporate culture is the whole of the basic values and beliefs shared in the institution, it consists of the habits, attitudes and behavior patterns shared by the institution and its employees, and includes shared beliefs, values and habitual behavior patterns. The accepted beliefs and acceptances of the institution to both newcomers and visitors summarize this point (Vechio, 1988:542).

The stronger the corporate culture, the more it performs and the easier it is to adapt to the goals of the institution, the stronger it is and the clearer its goals are understood by its employees, the ability to show appropriate attitudes and behaviors in case of uncertainty and its results (Sørensen, 2002: 73).). In other words, in a culture where the corporate culture is strong and adopted, the employees feel responsible and work devotedly by integrating them with the institution (Gümüştekin and Emet, 2007:92). As a result, as it is a system that shapes the feelings and thoughts of the employees who make up an institution, their behavior towards each other and their environment, and develops customary behaviors, the corporate culture ensures the participation of its members and strengthens team development by creating cooperation (Dinçer, 1995:402).

As the culture of the community consists of the values and beliefs accepted by the individuals as common, the corporate culture is the culture created by the founder and the employees in the institution. Safety culture, on the other hand, is the culture consisting of the attitudes and behaviors of the employees to ensure the safety of themselves and their colleagues (Erdoğan, 1983:113). Based on the conclusion that the corporate culture significantly affects the behaviors and habits of the employees when they are accepted and internalized by the employees of the institution and integrated with their own culture, it is obvious that the employees integrate with the institution and facilitate the realization of the objectives of the institution (Vural and Öksüz, 2016: 6). Based on the educational status of another demographic factor in the development of the perception of safety culture, and according to the results of the research, it was concluded that the safety culture perception of undergraduate graduates is higher than that of secondary school graduates. Because, it has been observed that the perception of safety culture is higher in employees who love their job than those who do not like their job. Considering similar

reasons, having employees who love their job in the workplace will help in improving the perception of occupational health and safety. The debate on the necessity of Public Relations has now ended in the world, and studies in Turkey show that the importance of public relations and corporate culture has not yet been understood, especially in small and medium-sized institutions. It is obvious that increasing the public relations activities of the institution for its own employees will provide an advantage in terms of maintaining and strengthening the institution. Because, if the institution itself does not establish a communication mechanism with its employees, the employees will establish informal communication networks among themselves. The function of public relations should be used for the employees of the institution. Because employees should get the right information about the institution from its source. Again, Tunca (2015) investigated the main cause-effect link in OHS culture and stated how the main problem and the imaginary problem are. Accordingly, by producing new concepts in the OHS culture, it established the main cause and effect link. Because OHS awareness was created, and recommendations were made for the solution of the problems. Enginoğlu (2015) examined the effect of leader and follower interaction on the creation of OHS culture in institutions, in construction works. also stated that awareness will be created.

Yüce (2014) examined the OHS culture in businesses operating in construction works. In his work, he examined the link between certain factors and culture. Aktay (2014) stated that creating a positive OHS safety culture, which will increase the level of counter-perception and create safe behaviors in creating a positive culture, will be an effective measure against OHS hazards.

It should be noted that in the absence of a public relations department, employees' awareness of organizational culture is low. It has been determined that there is a problem in data transfer between supervisors and subordinates. Gül (2014) encouraged the gendered approach in public relations firms to examine the theoretical and practical aspects of public relations activities at a university in the perspective of organizational culture and public relations practices and in the perspective of organizational culture, Kuraner (2011). When Hızır (1994) examined the function of organizational identity, organizational culture and visual identity in public relations planning in this context, Sancı (2005) revealed the necessity of examining corporate culture, public relations and in-house training practices. Skilled (1999) examined the effect of internal

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communication on the creation of corporate culture and discussed it with the concepts of internal and internal communication . According to the results, the effect of internal communication activities on corporate culture is open to discussion.

8. Conclusion

The data above, together with the analysis, tests and scales that we have given the results according to the research and criteria examples, together with the data in the literature, show that the social responsibility role and function of public relations in the creation of OHS culture has not been investigated. Although it is accepted in the world, the concept, title and sub-titles of a Public Relations Culture for Turkey do not fit or are not used appropriately, the fact that studies on public relations have been made on certain subjects does not present a generalization. This proves that the study and literature resources are not sufficient especially for Turkey and Turkish. Since a study that unites the issues of public relations, social responsibility and corporate culture is almost negligible, when the studies on OHS are examined, some studies are limited to technical requirements as well as to the legislation and legal dimension; It turns out that social sciences such as public relations, corporate culture and social responsibility, which can contribute significantly to occupational health and safety, are not sufficiently utilized. This study is a pioneering work with its feature of combining the fields of public relations, social responsibility, corporate culture and OHS. Again, since it is an original study in terms of adapting Archie Carroll's social responsibility pyramid to OHS culture, the data is presented as a summary, and the data is a reference for those working in the field of public relations and business to also turn to OHS, leading both the curriculum and other scientific studies in this regard. or encouraging. Likewise, those who work in the field of OHS will gain a key role and function in reducing work accidents and occupational diseases by turning to areas such as public relations, CSR, corporate culture.

Although it is the subject of another study, we obtain cognitive results based on the information and literature support above, regarding the prevention or reduction of occupational accidents and occupational diseases, and the need for OHS to become a culture in institutions and society.

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For OHS to become a culture, it is necessary for the individual to be constantly informed and conscious about OHS, starting from basic family education, in pre-school education, primary education, secondary education, higher education, non-formal education, in all public and private institutions . In this regard, it should be underlined that it is necessary to make it a culture by creating safe habits with safe behaviors. The role and function of public relations in relation to the formation of culture in institutions and society are also of indisputable importance. If this is exceeded, the better the communication of individuals, the stronger the bond between them, the higher their education and knowledge about OHS, the higher their risk perception will be, especially for Turkey. It would be appropriate to make the information about how this information can be prevented in the formation of work accidents and occupational diseases as a subject for other researches. Because the fact that many topics that take organizational culture and subcultures as sub-titles are not adapted for Turkish on time and in place confirms the mistakes, ignorance or deficiencies in practice of many studies that have examined organizational culture in a company that does not have a public relations department, by keeping them on the agenda.

9. Resources

- AKIN, L.: 2014 “Employer's Liability Resulting from Work Accident Fault
- AKTAY, N.: 2012 Relationship Between Occupational Health and Safety Education and Occupational Safety Culture, Assistant Labor Inspector Study, Istanbul.
- AKTAY, N.: 2012 Occupational Health and Safety Training and Occupational Safety
- ASNA, A.: 1993 Public Relations (Basic Information), Istanbul.
- ASNA, A.: 1993 Public Relations (Basic Information), Istanbul.
- ASNA, A.: 2012 Public Relations in Theory and Practice (Public
- AYDINLI, H. İ.: 2003 The Importance of Organizational Culture for Management, Bilgi, Vol:7, No:2, 77-99.

Ankara Bar Association Journal, Issue 2.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

BARON,RA: 1990 Behavior in Organizations, New Jersey, Prentice Hall,

BAYRAK, S.: 2001 Business Ethics and Social Responsibility, Istanbul, Beta

BIÇAKÇI, İ.: 2002 Communication and Public Relations, A Critical Approach.

BUDAK, G.: Public Relations from 2010 Image Engineering Vision.

Carroll's Evaluation of Social Responsibility Dimensions: An Application in Sivas Municipality", International Journal of Social Science, 360-372, Sivas.

ÇAĞLAR, İ.: 2001 "The Turkish Management Model in the Context of Management-Culture

Definitional Costruct, Business & Society, 38 (3), 268

Evaluation Methodologies, Ankara, Turkey Confederation of Employers' Unions,

DEMİR, E.: 2009 "Occupational Accidents Occurring in the Metal Business Line and Work

DEMİRBILEK, T.: 1999 Occupational Health and Safety Lecture Notes,

Izmir. DENISON, DR: 2004"Corporate Culture and Organizational Effectiveness",

DEMİRBILEK, T.: 2005 Occupational Safety Culture, 1st Edition, İzmir, Legal

DEMİRBILEK, T.: 2008 "Development of Occupational Safety Culture in Businesses",

DEMİRSOY, Ö.: 2012 "The Relationship Between Organizational Culture and Organizational Commitment".

DİNÇER, Ö., FİDAN, Y.: 1996 Introduction to Business Management, 2nd Edition, Istanbul: Beta Publications.

DİNÇER, Ö., FİDAN, Y.: 1995 Business Management, Istanbul, Beta Basım Dağıtım A.Ş.

EROĞLU, F.: 2015 Behavioral Sciences, 14th Edition, Istanbul, Beta Publishing.

GÜÇLÜ, N.: 2003 "Organization Culture", Kyrgyz Manas University, Journal of Social Sciences, 6, 147-159.

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

Homogeneity Of Personality Hypothesis”,
Journal of Applied Psychology, 83,
462-470

İNCİROĞLU, L.: 2008 Law of
Worker and Employer in
Occupational Health and Safety

KARA, Y.: 2006 School
Administrators of Organizational
Culture in Schools

KARAKÖSE, T.: 2007 Corporate DNA and
Reputation Management, Ankara,

Economical Analysis of the Losses Caused
by the Accidents ”, Master Thesis,
Istanbul. (“CAUSED BY
OCCUPATIONAL ACCIDENTS
AT A CONSTRUCTION SITE ... -
TRDizin ”)

KAZANCI, M.: 1999 Public
Relations, Ankara, Turhan Bookstore.
KAYALAR, M.,

KIRWAN, B.: 2011 “Incident Reduction
and Risk Migration”, Safety

KOZLU, C.: 1986 Corporate Culture:
America, Japan and Turkey:

KÖSE, S.: 2001 Factors Forming
Organizational Culture, Management
and

KURTZ, DL: 1992 Management, New
York, McGraw-Hill.

KÜÇÜKSARAÇ, B.: 2008 Public
Relations through the Internet in
Social Organizations, Master's
Thesis, Kocaeli University Institute of
Social Sciences.

MIHÇIOĞLU, C.: 1971 “What is
Public Relations?” Journal of Ankara
University Faculty of Education, 3(4):
91-108.

ÖKSÜZ, B.: 2008 “Corporate
Reputation Risk Management: Public
Relations

ÖKSÜZ, B.: 2014 “Institution Culture
and Public

ÖKSÜZ, B.: 2014 “Corporate Culture
and Public Relations”, New
Approaches in Public Relations. Ed.
Hale Bozkurt, Istanbul, Paradigma
Academy Publications,

Reforms”, Public Administration and
Public Policy,

ROBBINS, SP: 1993 Organizational
Behavior, USA, Prentice-Hall Inc.
RYAN, A.: 2000 Shaping A Safety
Culture, Queensland Mininig
Industry

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED
SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE
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353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

- ROBBINS, SP: 1993 Organizational Behavior, USA, Prentice-Hall Inc.
- RYAN, A.: 2000 Shaping A Safety Culture, Queensland Mining Industry
- role". Selcuk Communication, Vol. 5, no. 3, 111-123, VECHIO, R.: 1988 Organizational Behavior, NY, USA, Printice-Hall Inc.
- SABUNCUOĞLU, Z., TÜZ, M.: 1998 Organizational Psychology, Bursa, Alfa Publications. ("Organizational Change/Change | TR Index")
- SABUNCUOĞLU, Z., TÜZ, M.: 2013 Organizational Behavior, Bursa. Current Publications.
- SAYILI, M.: 2016 "Corporate Social Responsibility Perceptions of Employees,
- SCHEIN, EH: 2004 Organizational Culture And Leadership, San
- SCHEIN, EH: 1984 "Coming to a New Awareness of Organizational
- SCHERMERHORN,
- SCHNEIDER, B.: 1998 "Personality and Organizations: A Test of The
- ŞAHİN, A.: 2010 "Organizational Culture - Management Relationship and Managerial Efficiency".
- ŞAHİNGÖZ, S.: 2015 Occupational Health and Safety Basic According to Latest Legislation
- TORTOP, N.: 2009 Introduction to Public Relations. 10th Edition, Ankara, Nobel
- Toward the Moral Management of Organizational Stakeholders", Business Horizons, July-August, 39-48. ("Corporate Social Responsibility - SlideShare")
- TRIANDIS, HC: 2000 "Culture and Conflict". International Journal of
- TUTAR, H.: 2009 Organizational Communication. 2nd Edition, Ankara, Seçkin Publishing.
- TÜRKOĞLU, F.: 2006 Work Accidents and Occupational Diseases in Turkey
- VECHIO, R.: 1988 Organizational Behavior, NY, USA, Printice-Hall Inc.
- WATERMAN, RH: 1987 The Art of Managing and Upgrading: The Search for Perfection,

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE

WU, TC: 2010 “Predicting Safety
Culture: The Roles of Employer,

Approach”, Paradox, Journal of Economics,
Sociology and Politics, (e-journal),
ISSN 1305-7979, Year: 4 Issue: 1
January.

YİĞİT, A.: 2013 Occupational Safety,
Bursa, Dora Publishing.
YURDAKUL, NB,

Relation between Managerial Attitudes”.
Süleyman Demirel University Journal
of FEAS, Vol:12, No:3, 163-176.

YURDAKUL, NB: 2002 Basic Public
Relations Information, Ege
University